

Evapotranspiration and Transpiration Dynamics on Pedunculate Oak Stands in Spačva Forest Using MODIS Evapotranspiration

Nela Jantol^{1,*}, Tonko Megyery¹, Ana Đanić¹, Zrinka Mesić², Hrvoje Kutnjak³, Ivana Lampek Pavčnik¹

¹ Department of Nature Protection, Oikon Ltd. Institute of Applied Ecology, Zagreb, Croatia, njantol@oikon.hr

² Department of Wildlife Management and Nature Conservation, Karlovac University of Applied Sciences, Karlovac, Croatia

³ Division of Plant Science, Department of Field Crops, Forage and Grassland, University of Zagreb Faculty of Agriculture, Zagreb, Croatia

* corresponding author

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20407916

Abstract: The key variable in the water cycle, energy cycle, climate and carbon flow over land surfaces, and an important indicator of ecosystem functions and health is evapotranspiration (ET). It is defined as the total amount of water transported from land to the atmosphere and consists of evaporation from land and bodies of water (E) and plant transpiration (T). In 2019 and 2020, measurements of xylem sap flow were made in the Spačva forest (Croatia) of pedunculate oak on four plots, which can be linked to the T rate. T values measured in field were compared to satellite-based MODIS product MOD16A2GF with modelled ET. The maximum ET values measured by remote sensing were about 40 L m⁻² per 8 days. In the vegetation period up to the season transpiration maximum, MODIS ET successfully predicted T on all surfaces. Modelled T for all Spačva area was shown on maps where seasonal change and local differences can be observed. The results showed opportunities to use this product in monitoring of forest condition.

Keywords: water cycle; sap flow; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Evapotranspiration is an important factor in the terrestrial water cycle, influencing local and regional climate patterns and is essential for maintaining ecosystem productivity. Evapotranspiration is used to assess water resources, drive river basin hydrological models, study global climate and validate climate models (Bittencourt et al., 2023). Regional-scale evapotranspiration models vary in their estimates of the T/ET ratio, i.e. how much transpiration contributes to total evapotranspiration, with these values ranging from 0.45-0.75. Recent studies show that climate change is increasing the importance of vegetation in global water flow because plants influence extreme heat by regulating water and energy between the soil and the atmosphere (Keenan et al., 2023, Skinner et al., 2018).

Spačva Forest is an important area that encompasses diverse lowland habitats, with pedunculate oak as the dominant forest type, accounting for 96% of the total area. Located between the Sava and Danube rivers and their tributaries, this area represents one of the largest complexes of lowland pedunculate oak forests in Europe, extending over 40,000 ha. Since 2013, the invasive oak lace bug (*Corythucha arcuata*) (Say 1832) has also been present, causing damage to the tree canopy (Hrašovec et al., 2013).

This paper will study the dynamics of evapotranspiration and transpiration in the growing season for pedunculate

oak forests and the possibility of using remote sensing methods to monitor these phenomena.

2 Materials and methods

The Spačva forest is located mostly in Vukovar-Srijem County, and to a lesser extent in Brod-Posavina and Osijek-Baranja Counties (NW: 45.27, 18.49; SE: 44.94, 19.11, Figure 1). It is located between the Sava and Danube rivers in the basin of the Bosut River and its tributaries.

On four plots, each with five oak trees, the xylem sap flow was measured with the EMS 81 system (EMS Brno, Slovakia), which consists of a data logger (datalogger) MicroSet 8X, the device 'Sap FloWSF 81'. The trees circumference ranged from 137 to 267 cm, averaging 203 cm. Stand age in 2019. was from 116 to 132 years. Dominant species were pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*), with narrow-leaved ash (*Fraxinus angustifolia*) and European hornbeam (*Carpinus betulus*) being most abundant secondary species.

The sap-flow measurements were taken every 10 minutes. In the data processing, the values were averaged hourly and summed daily. The mean value of the eight-day sum values of xylem sap flow on all four plots was expressed as transpiration. For ET, the product MOD16A2GF, version 6.1, was used (Running et al. 2021) which contained modelled evapotranspiration for eight-day periods based on latent heat flux, with a spatial resolution of these layers of 500 m.

An initial Ordinary least squares (OLS) model was fitted for T and ET but showed significant residual autocorrelation (Durbin-Watson test), indicating that regression errors were temporally dependent. Therefore, inference was based on generalized least squares (GLS) models. Transpiration was finally modelled as a linear function of remotely sensed evapotranspiration using GLS framework with first-order autoregressive residual structure. This was done with 8-day average for T and ET for full vegetation season 2019 and 2020, pre-peak T (April to first week of July for both years) and post-peak T (first week of July to end of October for both years).

The chosen model was then applied to MODIS pixel grid with ET values in all the Spačva forest to get the modelled T. Maps for modelled T were created for the same period using R.

Figure 1. Results of the spectral indices.

3 Results

The maximum ET values measured by remote sensing were about 40 L m⁻² per 8 days (Figure 2) in middle June to July. In September, ET fell under 20 L m⁻² per 8 days. The most common T/ET ratio ranged from 0.3 to 0.5.

Pre-peak period showed the strongest coupling between ET and T and had the best model fit (lowest AIC). Post-peak period model was not statistically significant. All periods

showed positive temporal autocorrelation. Results from GLS models are shown in Table 1.

From the modelled T maps (Figure 3) it can be seen that transpiration rate was lower in early April and then it gradually increased. In middle April T rates were most heterogenous in the middle part of the forest and had lower T values. From middle June the T values were more homogenous, and few pixels had constantly larger values compared to others.

8-day average transpiration of pedunculate oak and evapotranspiration on plots in the vegetation period for 2019

Figure 2. Bar graph with 8-day average transpiration of pedunculate oak and evapotranspiration (MOD16A2GF) on plots in the vegetation period, data for 2019. Period 13.-21.8.2019. did not have measurements of T and is shown as a missing value.

Table 1. Results from General Least Squares (GLS) regression models.

Models	β_{ET}	SE	t	p	ϕ_{AR1}	AIC	Number of observations
Full season (2019 and 2020)	0.14	0.048	2.8996	0.0056	0.6918	224.8	51
Pre-peak (April-first week of July)	0.36	0.038	9.6439	< 0.001	0.3877	92.3	24
Post-peak (first week of July - end of October)	0.11	0.06	1.8121	0.082	0.6018	124.4	27

Figure 3. Modelled T from MODIS ET product MOD16A2GF for 8-day period from April to July 2019. Values of T are expressed as $L m^{-2}$ per 8 days. Model for T was created with generalized least squares model using average T measured in field on four plots and corresponding MOD16A2GF pixels.

4 Discussion

It was possible to use ET to predict T in a pedunculate oak forest where it was the dominant species, especially in the first part of the growing season. Global estimates of T/ET range from 45 to 75% (Schlesinger and Jasechko, 2014), and in our example they were somewhat lower. This can be attributed to the fact that T was measured only on pedunculate oak, but other species also contribute to the total T. In future studies of transpiration, it is recommended to measure it on other woody species as well as evaporation from the soil to separate ET into these two components.

From the beginning of September, T/ET increased, while total ET and T decreased towards the end of the season.

This means that T contributed more to the total ET towards the end of the season than in the previous period. This is in line with research by Wang et al. (2014) who observed higher T/ET in the later stages of the growing season at specific LAI values. They explained this by the fact that in the later stages leaves fall off and that there was more organic material on the soil, which reduced evaporation from the soil.

In middle of April, central part of Spačva forest had lower T values. This could be because of recent tree cutting according to the Croatian forests inventory database. The younger trees have smaller canopies, and they transpire less than older trees. Few pixels had constant higher values of T, even though the forest stands in these locations were younger. Since the model was created using data from four

plots with older trees (>100 years), it might not capture differences between canopies and layers in younger stands. On the other hand, if the lower values are caused by the stand age, using LiDAR, available for 2022/2023 (State Geodetic Administration) could reveal how the vegetation structure impacts T and/or ET.

Different stressors are present in Spačva area, from oak lace bug (detected in 2013), lowering of groundwater levels from 1980s, to major windthrows in 2008, 2019 and 2023. Remote sensing offers a way for frequent monitoring of these stressors and provides insight into how they affect transpiration levels.

5 Conclusions

Pedunculate oak in Spačva forest was a dominant tree species and its transpiration contributed significantly to the local evapotranspiration. Transpiration values were gradually increasing from April and peaked around end of June. It was possible to use the MOD16A2GF product to observe the dynamics of pedunculate oak transpiration in the Spačva forest in the period up to the seasonal peak of pedunculate oak transpiration, after which the model performance decreased.

Remote sensed products could be used for detecting larger variations in transpiration and plant stress.

Acknowledgments: Authors would like to express gratitude to Vladimir Kušan, PhD for creating the concept for sap flow measurements under the project Danube-Sava multipurpose canal and to ProSilva Ltd. for the forestry data and sap flow field measurements. Part of this data was used in Nela Jantol's PhD doctoral studies which was funded by Croatian Science Foundation DOK-2020-01-9841.

6 References

Bittencourt, P., Rowland, L., Sitch, S., Poyatos, R., Miralles, D.G.G., Mencuccini, M., 2023. Bridging Scales: An

Approach to Evaluate the Temporal Patterns of Global Transpiration Products Using Tree-Scale Sap Flow Data. *Journal of Geophysical Research-Biogeosciences* 128, e2022JG007308.

Hrašovec, B., Posarić, D., Lukić, I., Pernek, M., 2013. First record of oak lace bug (*Corythucha arcuata*) in Croatia. *Šumarski List* 137, 499–503.

Keenan, T.F., Luo, X., Stocker, B.D., De Kauwe, M.G., Medlyn, B.E., Prentice, I.C., Smith, N.G., Terrer, C., Wang, H., Zhang, Y., Zhou, S., 2023. A constraint on historic growth in global photosynthesis due to rising CO₂. *Nature Climate Change* 1–6.

Kern, A., Marjanović, H., Csóka, G., Móricz, N., Pernek, M., Hirka, A., Matošević, D., Paulin, M., Kovač, G., 2021. Detecting the oak lace bug infestation in oak forests using MODIS and meteorological data. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 306, 108436.

Myneni, R., Knyazikhin, Y., & Park, T., 2021. MODIS/Terra Leaf Area Index/FPAR 8-Day L4 Global 500m SIN Grid V061 [Data set]. NASA Land Processes Distributed Active Archive Center.

Running, W.S., Mu, Q., Zhao, M., Moreno, A., 2019. User's Guide MODIS Global Terrestrial Evapotranspiration (ET) Product (MOD16A2/A3 and Year-end Gap-filled MOD16A2GF/A3GF) NASA Earth Observing System MODIS Land Algorithm (For Collection 6). Version 2.2.

Schlesinger, W.H., Jasechko, S., 2014. Transpiration in the global water cycle. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 189–190, 115–117.

Skinner, C.B., Poulsen, C.J., Mankin, J.S., 2018. Amplification of heat extremes by plant CO₂ physiological forcing. *Nature*

Wang, L., Good, S.P., Caylor, K.K., 2014. Global synthesis of vegetation control on evapotranspiration partitioning. *Geophysical Research Letters* 41, 6753–6757.